

Subadult Virtual Anthropology Database (SVAD) Data Collection Protocol: Landmark Placement on Virtual 3D Crania

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This document presents the standardized protocol developed to place cranial landmarks and collect cranial landmark coordinates on 3D renderings of subadult crania obtained from computed tomography scans. This protocol was developed as part of National Institute of Justice Award 2019 DU-BX-0039. If the methodology presented herein is used or mentioned in a presentation or publication, then this document needs to be cited. Additionally, we strongly encourage all research using this protocol to be submitted to the Subadult Virtual Anthropology Database (SVAD) Zenodo Community to facilitate sharing and discovery of information (<https://zenodo.org/communities/svad/?page=1&size=20>).

Data

Forty-eight craniometric landmarks are placed on virtual crania. Interlandmark distances (ILDs) from 3D landmark coordinates (x,y,z) are calculated as:

$$ILD = \sqrt{(x_1-x_2)^2 + (y_1-y_2)^2 + (z_1-z_2)^2}$$

with (x₁, y₁, z₁) the coordinates of the first landmark and (x₂, y₂, z₂) the coordinates for the second landmark.

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Landmark Definitions

All landmark definitions follow Howells (1973) and Langley et al. (2016) though some commentary for placement on virtual subjects is provided. There are both midline and paired landmarks defined and visualized below (Table 1 and Figures 1 - 4). Abbreviations are provided with the definition; the paired landmarks usually have a 'r' and 'l' that indicate the side. Placement order is provided in Table 2.

Table 1 - Names of the 48 cranial landmarks	
Midline landmarks	Paired landmarks (Left and Right)
Basion	Alare
Bregma*	Asterion*
Glabella	Cheek Height Superior Point*
Hormion	Cheek Height Inferior Point*
Lambda	Dacryon*
Nasion	Ectoconchion*
Opisthocranion*	Euryon*
Opisthion	Foramen Magnum Breadth
Prosthion	Frontomalare Anterior
Subspinale	Frontotemporale*
	Jugale
	M1 anterior point*
	Mastoideale
	Most Inferior Nasal Border
	Orbital Height Inferior Point*
	Orbital Height Superior Point*
	Porion
	Radiculare
	Zygion*

* These landmarks have additional instructions to help with placement. Please see the comments in the "Placing landmarks in Amira™" section for more details

Definitions and Abbreviations

** These landmarks have additional instructions to help with placement. Please see the comments in the "Placing landmarks in Amira™" section (p. 11) for more details*

- **Alare** (bilateral) (**alarl or alarr**): the most lateral left or right points on the nasal aperture in the transverse plane
- **Asterion*** (bilateral) (**astl or astr**): intersection of the occipital, left or right temporal, and left or right parietal bones
- **Basion (bas)**: midline point of the anterior margin of the foramen magnum, opposite the opisthion (most anterior point of the margin)
- **Bregma brg**: the ectocranial midline point where coronal and sagittal sutures meet
- **Cheek Height Inferior Point*** (bilateral) (**wmhil or wmlir**): the lower left or right margin of the maxilla, medial to the masseter attachment (superior point), to obtain the minimum distance to the lower border of the left and right orbit (minimum cheek height)
- **Cheek Height Superior Point*** (bilateral) (**wmhsl or wmsr**): the lower border of the left or right orbit to obtain the minimum distance to the lower left or right margin of the maxilla, medial to the masseter attachment (superior point) (minimum cheek height)
- **Dacryon*** (bilateral) (**dacl or dacr**): the point on the medial border of the left or right orbit at which the frontal, lacrimal and maxilla intersect/ intersection of the frontal bone and lacrimo-maxillary suture/ the apex of the lacrimal fossa where the suture would be if not visible
- **Ectoconchion*** (bilateral) (**ectl or ectr**): the intersection of the most anterior surface of the lateral border of the left or right orbit and a line bisecting the orbit along its horizontal axis.
- **Euryon*** (bilateral) (**eurl or eurr**): the extremity, on either side, of the greatest transverse diameter of the skull
- **Foramen Magnum Breadth** (bilateral) (**fmb1 or fmb2**): the left or right most lateral part of the margin of the foramen magnum
- **Frontomolare Anterior** (bilateral) **fmal or fmar**: the most anterior points of the left or right fronto-malar (fronto-zygomatic) suture
- **Frontotemporale*** (bilateral) (**wfbl or wfbr**): the point where the left or right temporal line reaches its most anteromedial position on the frontal bone
- **Glabella (glb)**: the most anterior midline point of the frontal bone proximal to the orbital torus
- **Hormion hor**: intersection of the midsagittal plane and the line where the base of vomer meets the sphenoid
- **Jugale** (bilateral) (**jugl or jugr**): the point at the union of the left or right frontal and temporal processes of the malar (zygomatic) bone
- **Lambda (lam)**: Intersection of the sagittal and lambdoid sutures in the midsagittal plane
- **Mastoideale** (bilateral) (**mastl or mastr**): inferior extrema of the left and right mastoid process
- **M1 Anterior Point*** (bilateral) (**avrptl or avrptr**): the most anterior point on the lateral side of the alveolus of the left or right first permanent molars. If there is resorption or damage to the alveolar border, an estimate of its original extent must be made. Where most teeth are missing, be certain that the correct alveolus is being used by counting from the midline. If the permanent M1 is not emerged, place this point posteriorly to the emerged deciduous second molar (dm2). If dm2 is not emerged, do not place this point.

- **Nasion (nas)**: intersection of the frontal and nasal sutures in the midsagittal plane
- **Most Inferior Nasal Border** (bilateral)(**nlhil or nlhir**): lowest left or right points on the border of the nasal aperture
- **Opisthion (ops)**: midpoint of the posterior margin of the foramen magnum in the midsagittal plane (most posterior point of the margin)
- **Opisthocranium*** (**opg**): the most posterior point of the skull not on the external occipital protuberance
- **Orbital Height Inferior Point*** (**obhil or obhir**): the left or right most inferior points of the margin of the ocular orbit
- **Orbital Height Superior Point*** (**obhsl or obhsr**): the left or right most superior points of the margin of the ocular orbit.
- **Porion** (bilateral) (**porl or porr**): point superior to the left or right external auditory meatus, also may be determined by the posterior root of the zygomatic arch
- **Prosthion (prosM)**: the most anterior point in the midsagittal plane between the upper incisor alveolar processes
- **Radiculare** (bilateral) (**aubl or aubr**): the point on the lateral aspect of the left or right root of the zygomatic process at the deepest incurvature (best viewed inferiorly)
- **Subspinale (ssp)**: deepest point directly inferior to the projection of the nasal spine
- **Zygion*** (bilateral) (**zygl or zygr**): the most laterally positioned point on the left or right zygomatic arches (best viewed inferiorly)

Table 2 – Landmark placement numbers and abbreviations

<i>Number</i>	<i>Landmark</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Landmark</i>
1	Prosthion (prosm)	25	Frontomolare Anterior R (fmar)
2	Subspinale (ssp)	26	Jugale R (jugr)
3	Alare L (alarl)	27	Nasion (nas)
4	Most Inferior Nasal Border L (nlhil)	28	Glabella (glb)
5	Most Inferior Nasal Border R (nlhir)	29	Bregma (brg)
6	Alare R (alarr)	30	Lambda (lam)
7	Ectoconchion L (ectl)	31	Asterion L (astl)
8	Orbit Height Inferior L (obhil)	32	Eurion L (eurl)
9	Orbit Height Superior L (obhsl)	33	Porion L (porl)
10	Cheek Height Superior Point L (wmhsl)	34	Mastoideale L (mastl)
11	Cheek Height Inferior Point L (wmhil)	35	Radiculare L (aubl)
12	Dacryon L (dacl)	36	Radiculare R (aubr)
13	Dacryon R (dacr)	37	Porion R (porr)
14	Ectoconchion R (ectr)	38	Mastoideale R (mastr)
15	Orbit Height Inferior R (obhir)	39	Eurion R (eurr)
16	Orbit Height Superior R (obhsr)	40	Asterion R (astr)
17	Cheek Height Superior Point R (wmhsr)	41	Opisthocranium (opg)
18	Cheek Height Inferior Point R (wmhir)	42	Opisthion (ops)
19	Zygion L (zygl)	43	Foramen Magnum Breadth L (fmbl)
20	Zygion R (zygr)	44	Foramen Magnum Breadth R (fmbr)
21	Jugale L (jugl)	45	Basion (bas)
22	Frontomolare Anterior L (fmal)	46	Hormion (hor)
23	Frontotemporale L (wfbl)	47	M1 Anterior Point L (avrptl)
24	Frontotemporale R (wfbr)	48	M1 Anterior Point R (avrptr)

Fig. 2: Left lateral view of cranio-facial landmarks (paired in blue, midline in red). Numbers correspond to landmark placement order.

Fig. 3: Right lateral view of cranio-facial landmarks (paired in blue, midline in red). Numbers correspond to landmark placement order.

Fig. 4. Basal view of crano-facial landmarks (paired in blue, midline in red). Numbers correspond to landmark placement order.

Data collection in Amira™

1. Opening Amira™.

Click on the “**Project**” tab to open a workspace. Before selecting anything else, click the perspective button. The button is located in a bar of other buttons just above the viewing panes and looks like an eye: . Use the parallel line setting for all specimen editing and measuring. **You have to reset this every time you reopen Amira™.**

Choose [*Open Data...*] (green button in the “**Project View**” pane in the upper left corner).

2. Loading a stack of CT scans.

Find the individual you are interested in and select all of the DICOMs in that folder (NB: not the DICOM directory). **Click [Open]**. Always select the folder that has “ST” in the name. This stands for “Soft Tissue” and has a better resolution than “Bone”. You can choose folders with names including “Head, Head-Neck”, or “Whole Body” as they all include the upper body and skull.

If you get a warning about the file size being too large, choose the radio button for “Load complete volume into memory” and **click [OK]**.

A dialog box called “**DICOM Loader**” will prompt you to check the parameters of the DICOM stack. Scroll through the window and if everything looks good (not out of order numbering, gaps in the data, etc.), **click [OK]**. Any errors will be shown as red numbers in the list of DICOMs. If that is the case, only select the DICOM files that appear in black by pressing shift and clicking on the first and last DICOM of the stack that you want to open.

3. Visualizing the CT slices.

The file appears as a green lozenge in the “**Project View**” pane. Select the orange [**Orthoslice**] tab in the “**Project View**” pane. The CT slice should appear in the viewing console on the right. You can change the plane of the slice view by selecting xy, xz, or yz in the console header. If the hand is selected in that header, you can use it to move the exam around. You can also scroll through the slices by clicking the **box next to the Slice Number line** in the “Properties” pane and using the mouse to scroll or moving the cursor between the two triangles.

4. Creating a Volume Rendering of the skull.

Select the green lozenge. Click on the yellow [**Volume Rendering**] button. The soft tissue of the scanned body should appear in the viewing console on the right. You can use the mouse on hand mode to turn the body around at different angles.

In the “**Properties**” pane, move the left cursor of the “**Colormap**” higher to adjust the masking value (the number on the left). This allows you to hide soft tissue and only visualize bones or teeth (200-500 HU), the further you adjust the value. Higher values will only allow to visualize

the densest elements (metal, teeth, etc.). You can also type a value in that left box and lower the right slider as well. If you cannot see the teeth, you can move the body around and/or unselect the orange square in the [**Orthoslice**] lozenge to hide the contents of the CT slice. A good range of values should encompass part of the grey peaks you can see in the “**Colormap**”.

To adjust the transparency, in the “**Properties**” pane, click on the [**Edit box**] of the Colormap line. You can scroll down the menu and choose one of the colormap options. You can always revert back to the original setting if necessary by selecting it in the “**Edit**” box.

5. Creating an Isosurface of the skull (optional).

If the volume rendering visualization isn't satisfactory, click on the yellow [**Volume Rendering Settings**] lozenge that appeared and select the Isosurface Rendering button at the top of the “**Project View**” pane. Click on the **small orange square** of the [**Volume Rendering**] lozenge to hide it.

Select the *Isosurface Rendering* lozenge again. In the “**Threshold**” section, move the slider to adjust the masking value (the number on the right). This allows you to hide soft tissue and only visualize bones, the further you adjust the value. Higher values will only allow to visualize the densest elements (metal, teeth, etc.). You can also type a value in the box. If you cannot see the bones, you can move the body around and/or unselect the orange square in the [**Orthoslice**] lozenge to hide the CT slice.

6. Some adjustments.

To adjust the transparency, select the [**Volume Rendering**] lozenge. In the “**Properties**” pane, **click on the [Edit box]** of the “Colormap” line. You can scroll down the menu and choose one of the Colormap options. You can revert back if necessary at any point.

You can also do this by adjusting the value of “**Opacity**” below (from 0 to 1)

Comments

If you need to hide some parts of the body to facilitate scoring (like lower jaw, half of the skull, upper teeth, vertebrae, ribs, etc.), *select the orange Orthoslice* lozenge. In the “**Properties**” pane, click on the icon that looks like a cube with a green line crossing it (**the Clip tool**). Click on it once to hide half of the body, click on it again to see the full body and click on it a third time to see the other half of the body. You can do this in every plane, by changing the plane from xy to xz and yz in the “**Orientation**” line and in the viewing console while the [**Orthoslice**] lozenge is selected and by keeping that Clip tool selected. This will hide whatever structures are in front or behind the slice in question.

To scroll through that subset of the reconstruction, select the [**Orthoslice**] lozenge and go through “**Slice Number**” in the “**Properties**” pane.

These combinations of the different plane views of the [**Orthoslice**] and the **Clip tool** help you hide/see particular structures to facilitate scoring. Play around with all three planes and the clip tool to change views as needed.

If you want to hide the slice contents from view and only see the reconstruction, click on the small orange box of the [**Orthoslice**] lozenge. Click it back to visualize slice contents.

If you want to hide more of the bone and the less dense parts of the teeth to improve visualization of the roots for example, you can further adjust the threshold value in the “**Colormap**” to a higher range.

7. Creating the landmarks file.

In the “**Project**” pane, go to *Project -> Create Object -> Points and Lines -> Landmarks -> Create*. A new green lozenge called “*Landmarks*” appears. Select the green lozenge, then go to the “**Properties**” pane below and select the CT file Image Set1. **Click on the little icon with the red flag in that same pane** and a yellow lozenge will appear. You can adjust the size of the landmark here by moving the cursor for “**Size**”.

8. Saving landmark data.

Amira™ has a tendency to crash when in overload. To avoid losing your ongoing work, save the landmarks file initially by selecting the corresponding *Landmarks* lozenge and going to *File-> Save data as* and **save the file as “identifier_xxx_cranial_landmarks” in landmarkAscii format**. Then do the same thing to save it regularly throughout your session.

9. Placing landmarks.

Select the green Landmarks lozenge. Make sure the **Edit** mode in the “**Properties**” pane is set to “**Add**”. With the hand icon selected in the right pane where the segmented surface is, move the cranium until it is in the right position to place a landmark. Select the cursor at the top of that same pane. **Click on the cranium where you want to place the landmark**. NB: If you need to adjust the size, select the yellow Landmarks lozenge and change the size using the cursor.

If you need to change the position of the landmark, select the green lozenge and change Edit Mode to “Move”. Make sure the cursor is selected at the top of the right viewing pane. **Click on the landmark you want to move and click in the new spot you want to move them to**.

When you want to add a new landmark, **change the “Edit Mode” to “Add” and click on the cranium to add it**.

If you move a landmark after having placed others, it will not change the order of placement.

You can **check how many landmarks** you have already placed as you go along. That number appears next to “**Landmarks Set**” in the “**Properties**” pane.

Comments/Suggestions/Friendly Reminders for Placing Landmarks

- Make sure that:
 - **The green lozenge and the arrow are selected every time you are working on the landmarks.** Switch between the cursor to place the landmarks and the hand to move the cranium around.
 - **You always place landmarks in the same order, as we export the data and require the landmarks to be in the same order every time for analyses.**
 - **If you cannot place a landmark at its correct location on the cranium because of image resolution/reconstruction quality, trauma or structure immaturity,** place the landmark in an area of the CT slice that is far enough from the cranium so it cannot be considered a misplacement, for example, in one of its corners. Group all “NA” landmarks in that same area.
 - **Save your landmarks file regularly.** The disappearance of the * symbol on the Landmarks lozenge will inform you that the file was saved successfully.
- **To help you with visualization or hide parts of the skeleton that are blocking your view** of a particular structure, use the Orthoslice and the Clip Tool. Select the orange [Orthoslice] lozenge then go to the “Properties” pane below and click on the [Clip tool] in the upper right corner (the icon that looks like a cube with a green line crossing it. This will change the icon to a half-cube and will hide the structures that are on one side of the slice indicated in the “Slice Number” line. If you click back on the [Clip Tool], the structures will reappear. If you click once more, the structures on the opposite side of the slice will be hidden. You can change the plane of the slice by selecting one of the three options in the “Orientation” line (xy, xz, yz) and use the clip tool in either plane. To change views, go to the top of the “Viewing” pane and select one of the three Views (xy, xz, or yz).
- Use the Amira™ measuring tool to find the position of the following points (see below). At the top of the “Viewing” pane, click on the ruler icon to open up the measuring tool. A yellow [Measurement] lozenge should appear in “Project View”. Click on it and select the Measurement in the “Properties” pane below. Go to the “Viewing” pane and click on the location where you would place the first point then click on the location you would place the second point. You can move the measurement by clicking on both locations again.
 - To place **Frontotemporale (wfbl and wfbr)**, look at the cranium from an oblique superior view to visualize the post-orbital constriction/point of deepest inflection/minimal frontal width. Use the [Measurement] tool to ensure you have the minimum distance.
 - To place **Opisthocranium (opg)**: from a lateral view, position it as the furthest point from Glabella on the occipital bone using the measuring tool.
 - **Left and right Euryon (eurl and eurr)** for maximum cranial width. Place a point on the **Left** that is visually at the greatest breadth from a Superior view. Find the maximum width to the other side, modifying point placement on either side until maximum is obtained.
 - Left and right **Cheek height Superior points (wmhsl or wmhsr) and Cheek Height Inferior points (wmhil or wmhir)** for cheek height. Measure the minimum

distance from the inferior orbital margin to the inferior maxilla. **wmhs** is independent of **obhi** and may or may not be located at the same point.

- Left and right **Ectoconchion** and **Superior (obhs1 or obhsr) and Inferior Orbital Height (obhil or obhir)** so that orbital height (**obhs-obhi**) is perpendicular to orbital width (**dac-ect**) with both measurements bisecting the orbits. First, bisect the orbit in half transversally along the axis of the orbit: **ect** to a **point medial** that divides the orbit into roughly equal superior and inferior halves. Note, this point could be **dacryon**, but not necessarily. Next, measure a line perpendicular to this plane from **obhs-obhi** that divides the orbit into roughly 4 equal quadrants. The lateral point is **ectoconchion**, superior is **obhs**, and inferior is **obhi**. Note, **obhi** and **obhs** are relative to the positioning of **ect**.

- Left and right **Zygion (zygl or zygr)** for bizygomatic breadth measured using the measuring tool.
- To place **M1 anterior points (avrptl and avrptr)**: use [Orthoslice] to see where the alveolus for M1 is located and place the points accordingly. If M1 or dm2 are not erupted, do not place these points.
- To place **Dacryon (dacr and dacl)** and **Asterion (astl and astr)**, adjust the thresholds as follows:
 - Decrease the masking value to place **Dacryon** to visualize the apex of the lacrimal fossa and ethmoid
 - Increase the masking value to place **Asterion** to visualize the sutures as much as possible.
- To place **Bregma (brg)**, left and right **frontomolare anterior (fmal and fmar)** and left and right **Asterion (astl and astr)** on unfused individuals (presence of fontanelles) or if the sutures are not clearly visible, decrease the masking value to visualize the cartilage of both fontanelles and place accordingly by virtually prolonging the suture lines to find where they intersect. In case of wormian bones or fuzzy sutures, increase the masking value so they become visible, prolong the sutures until their meeting point and place the landmark accordingly.

10. Saving the data and the project

Once all landmarks have been placed, go to *File > Save Project* as an .hx file. When saving, a [Dialog] box may pop up that notes if you haven't saved aspects of the project that would need to get saved in order to re-open the project. **Save the files using the same name and into the same folder where the rest of the data (landmarks) for this specimen are stored.**

11. Finishing steps

Select all lozenges by **clicking and holding the left side of the mouse** and then dragging the mouse over them. Drag everything to the trashcan, in the lower right corner of the Project View pane. *Start over again with a new individual!*

Saving the data in a csv/Excel spreadsheet and in RDS format

1. Transposing the landmark coordinates into a csv spreadsheet

Download the template file named “**SVAD_Cranial_Landmarks.csv**” from the SVAD webpage (<https://www.unr.edu/anthropology/research-and-facilities/subadult-database>) and open it with the Excel application.

This file is organized as follows:

- Column one holds the identifier number, *i.e.* the individual that landmark data were collected for. By default, the template will have xxx and yyy as two exemplary identifiers. These identifiers are repeated 48 times, one for each of the 48 landmarks collected.
- Column two holds the abbreviations of the 48 cranial landmarks. There should be 48 lines corresponding to the 48 landmarks for each individual, repeated for every individual.
- Columns three to five hold the 3D coordinates (x,y,z) of each landmark (x in column three, y in column four, and z in column five).

2. Adding the landmark data to the csv spreadsheet

Locate the “**identifier_cranial_landmarks.ascii**” file for the individual the landmark data was collected.

Right click on that file and open it using the Notepad application. It should show the x, y and z coordinate sets for each landmark grouped in the correct order.

If necessary, adjust the window to visualize the coordinates in three columns in Notepad so you have one landmark per row (there should be a total of 48 rows here) and the coordinates start below the @1 symbol (see figure below).

Highlight/select the x,y,z coordinates of all 48 landmarks, as visualized below.

```
# Avizo 3D ASCII 3.0

define Markers 48

Parameters {
  NumSets 1,
  ContentType "LandmarkSet"
}

Markers { float[3] coordinates } @1

# Data section follows
@1
1.218554687500000e+001 8.776562500000000e+001 -1.580000000000000e+002
1.087695312500000e+001 8.645703125000000e+001 -1.420000000000000e+002
2.134570312500000e+001 8.972851562500000e+001 -1.340000000000000e+002
1.676562500000000e+001 8.841992187500000e+001 -1.385000000000000e+002
3.679687500000000e+000 8.841992187500000e+001 -1.395000000000000e+002
2.208984375000000e+000 8.972851562500000e+001 -1.360000000000000e+002
4.882617187500000e+001 1.028144531250000e+002 -1.080000000000000e+002
2.788867187500000e+001 9.430859375000000e+001 -1.185000000000000e+002
3.574023437500000e+001 9.365429687500000e+001 -8.550000000000000e+001
4.097460937500000e+001 9.692578125000000e+001 -1.190000000000000e+002
4.555468750000000e+001 1.093574218750000e+002 -1.360000000000000e+002
1.545703125000000e+001 9.561718750000000e+001 -1.045000000000000e+002
3.517578125000000e+000 9.496289062500000e+001 -1.075000000000000e+002
3.688671875000000e+001 1.041230468750000e+002 -1.125000000000000e+002
1.725781250000000e+001 9.561718750000000e+001 -1.245000000000000e+002
2.510937500000000e+001 9.365429687500000e+001 -9.100000000000000e+001
2.641796875000000e+001 9.888867187500000e+001 -1.260000000000000e+002
2.641796875000000e+001 1.073945312500000e+002 -1.440000000000000e+002
6.387500000000000e+001 1.283320312500000e+002 -1.195000000000000e+002
```

Press ctrl+C to copy and ctrl+V to paste the coordinates in the x column of the csv spreadsheet. This should fill the x column for the entire set of landmarks of that identifier. Confirm there are 48 rows with the same identifier and there are 48 landmark abbreviations in column two, and the landmark coordinate values in column three.

1	identifier	landmark	x	y	z
2	xxx	prosM	1.218554687500000e+001	8.77656250000000e+001	-1.58000000000000e+002
3	xxx	ssp	1.087695312500000e+001	8.64570312500000e+001	-1.42000000000000e+002
4	xxx	alarl	2.134570312500000e+001	8.97285156250000e+001	-1.34000000000000e+002
5	xxx	nlhil	1.67656250000000e+001	8.84199218750000e+001	-1.38500000000000e+002
6	xxx	nlhir	3.67968750000000e+000	8.84199218750000e+001	-1.39500000000000e+002
7	xxx	alarr	-2.20898437500000e+000	8.97285156250000e+001	-1.36000000000000e+002
8	xxx	ectfl	4.88261718750000e+001	1.02814453125000e+002	-1.08000000000000e+002
9	xxx	obhil	2.78886718750000e+001	9.43085937500000e+001	-1.18500000000000e+002
10	xxx	obhsl	3.57402343750000e+001	9.36542968750000e+001	-8.55000000000000e+001
11	xxx	wmhs1	4.09746093750000e+001	9.69257812500000e+001	-1.19000000000000e+002
12	xxx	wmhil	4.55546875000000e+001	1.09357421875000e+002	-1.36000000000000e+002
13	xxx	dacl	1.54570312500000e+001	9.56171875000000e+001	-1.04500000000000e+002
14	xxx	dacr	-3.51757812500000e+000	9.49628906250000e+001	-1.07500000000000e+002
15	xxx	ectr	-3.68867187500000e+001	1.04123046875000e+002	-1.12500000000000e+002
16	xxx	obhir	-1.72578125000000e+001	9.56171875000000e+001	-1.24500000000000e+002
17	xxx	obhsr	-2.51093750000000e+001	9.36542968750000e+001	-9.10000000000000e+001
18	xxx	wnhsr	-2.64179687500000e+001	9.88886718750000e+001	-1.26000000000000e+002
19	xxx	wmhir	-2.64179687500000e+001	1.07394531250000e+002	-1.44000000000000e+002
20	xxx	zygl	6.38750000000000e+001	1.28332031250000e+002	-1.19500000000000e+002
21	xxx	zygr	-4.67011718750000e+001	1.28332031250000e+002	-1.31000000000000e+002
22	xxx	jugl	5.53691406250000e+001	1.12628906250000e+002	-1.13500000000000e+002
23	xxx	fmal	4.75175781250000e+001	1.01505859375000e+002	-9.60000000000000e+001
24	xxx	wfbl			

While the values are still selected in Excel, go to **Data-> Data tools** and click on **“Text to Columns”**. Make sure the option checked is **“Fixed width”**, then click **“Next”**.

Excel should have automatically identified the break line between the values as shown by lines running through the data, effectively separating x, y, and z values. If not, directly click where the break lines should be to separate all three values for the x,y,z coordinates.

Make sure the lines are placed correctly (*i.e.*, not cutting through any numbers that shouldn't be separated). When you have confirmed it is correct, click **“Next”** and then **“Finish”**. Your x, y, z data should now be separated into columns three to five.

Check that all rows corresponding to the identifier (one row per landmark) are filled. If stars (***) or octothorpes (###) appear instead of the values, do not worry. If you select a cell, the correct values will appear in the fx bar.

3. Missing landmark coordinates

Since you placed the NA landmarks in the same spot in Amira, their coordinates should be relatively similar (x,y, and/or z). You will have to manually replace missing landmark coordinates in the spreadsheet by writing NA for the x,y,z values as needed.

Repeat steps 2 and 3 for each individual/identifier you wish to add to the dataset. Remember to update the name of the spreadsheet with each identifier that is added to it (*e.g.*, “**projectname_typeofdata_identifierxxx_yyy**”) and save it regularly as you fill it in.

4. Saving the csv file in RDS format

Because csv files can be easily corrupted, it is recommended to save each csv file on a regular basis into RDS format.

To do this, open RStudio and run the following code:

```
library(tidyr)
```

```
library(dplyr)
```

```
library(readr)
```

```
library(base)
```

- If you haven't installed these packages before, please do so prior by running the code:
`install.packages("package_name")`

```
#Load old csv file and save it as a RDS file
```

```
File_name <- read_csv("~/path/to/database/File_name.csv")
```

```
write_rds(File_name, "~/path/ to/database/File_name.rds", row.names=FALSE)
```

- The new RDS file will be automatically created in that location (following the path you wrote).

Create a copy of the csv file prior to additional data collection and collect in the new copy.

Update the last identifier number every time you modify it (*i.e.*,

“**projectname_typeofdata_identifier_xxx_yyy**” to

“**projectname_typeofdata_identifier_xxx_zzz**”). That way, data is added on a regular/weekly basis and if something happens to the file, you can always revert to the previous one as a backup. You will then save each new weekly csv file as a RDS file so you have backups in RDS formats.

References

Howells, WW. (1973). *Cranial Variation in Man. A Study by Multivariate Analysis of Patterns of Differences Among Recent Human Populations*. 67 vols. Cambridge, Mass.: Peabody Museum.: Papers of the Peabody Museum of Archeology and Ethnology.

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